

ORGANIZATIONAL MODEL BASED ON CONFLICT PREVENTION IN INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

¹Ibraimov Kholboy Ibragimovich, ²Eshquvvatov Tolqinjon Eshquvvatovich

¹Pedagogy named after T.N.Kori Niyazi director
scientific research institute, p.f.d. Professor

²Head of the Department of “Pre-school and primary education, sports”, Kattakorgan Branch of
Samarkand State University (PhD)

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Abstract. *The article deals with pedagogical conflicts, the nature of pedagogical conflicts in universities, their immediate causes and their analysis, organizational and managerial conflicts, ways to resolve them, and the art of managing them. psychological service and we think that this will help future teachers methodically*

Keywords: *higher education system, innovation, innovative development, conflicts of innovative development*

Based on the fact that education in the world is not only a manifestation of the level of intellectuality, but also a factor of social culture that expresses interpersonal relations, it is necessary to organize and conduct educational processes in a conflict-free manner, to form the appropriate competencies of students in their specialty, to develop their creative abilities. special attention is being paid to the elimination of conflict situations in development.

Today, special attention is paid to the integration of innovation into the organizational and pedagogical conditions of educational processes, including the development of higher education institutions based on innovative trends.

The higher education system, compared to other educational institutions, is distinguished by the diversity of interpersonal and group relations in terms of tasks. The complexity and uncertainty of these relations can be seen in the coverage of pedagogical, social, psychological, economic, legal and many other spheres of life. It is natural that such diversity creates conflicts of interests, attitudes, opinions, positions and human needs.

According to O.A.Danilevich, the main task of higher education is to increase the quality of training specialists who are ready to solve non-standard problems, identify priorities, perceive innovations and make the right decisions. the educational system should be open to modern scientific research and modern economy, the technological equipment of the educational process should correspond to the level of advanced science [4; 134-140 b].

O.Yu.Gordashnikova, in her recommendations on organizing the evaluation and analysis of the innovative development of higher education institutions, emphasized the need to select the comparative indicators of relevant criteria based on the principles that ensure continuity, reliability, objectivity, optimality and completeness. focuses on [2;60-64b].

According to T.P.Gorelova, the indicators of the innovative potential of the university include: efficiency of scientific and innovative activity; teaching status; intellectual potential of the university; availability of material and information base [3; 38-39 b].

In the literature, as educational innovations, the effectiveness of the teacher's work, constructive approach, effective management of knowledge, support for the teacher's work, online teaching, informal method, social media, educational games, pedagogical skill, Hemis platform, teaching in the credit-module system, teaching in mobile mode, etc.

A.A.Engovatova, who conducted research on the organization of the innovative infrastructure of higher education institutions, focused on the Foreside Center, design activity management, intellectual property management, marketing, business incubator, collective use of equipment and prototypes, technopark, business school, financing fund. considered as elements of innovative development [8; 26-b].

In the innovative development of higher education institutions, it is important to implement a set of measures aimed at in-depth study of the internal and external environment, to ensure organizational stability and to achieve the necessary dynamics of innovative processes, to be based on the internal organizational integration of all subjects, innovative infrastructure and information systems plays a role [1; 6-17].

The main task of educational work and scientific activity in the innovative development of higher education institutions is to actively introduce technological approaches to the processes of obtaining, distributing and applying new knowledge. In this process, there is a need for high-level training of professors, specialists and students, formation of appropriate skills and information culture, and research activity. In particular, the effective participation of professors and teachers as the main subject in the application of teaching technologies and interactive methods that lead to innovative thinking, and mechanisms that support students' independent learning is important.

Any higher education institution on the path of innovative development implements information technology and digitization processes. These processes are carried out directly on the basis of the formation of a common information space, the high level of use of information and communication technologies in the educational and management environment, the creation of a database and its continuous updating, as well as ensuring its integration into the fields of activity.

Monitoring the quality of education involves a quick assessment of the current situation and a reasonable determination of the future directions of development through a thorough analysis of the results.

The above indicates that the model of innovative development of higher education institutions requires deep integration, and that this model implements mechanisms to increase real competitiveness based on improving the quality of education and innovative activities. Innovation-based models of higher education institutions serve to ensure the development of national economies.

Innovative activity in a higher educational institution is carried out on the basis of mutual pedagogical relations of the subjects of the educational process, any innovative approach affects the relations of the subjects, is considered relevant.

It is also necessary to take into account that the demands of reforming the educational system and innovative development may cause various conflict situations in pedagogical relations in higher education institutions. The complexity of the conflict situations that arise in the process of innovative development is that it is difficult to coordinate it with the nature of traditional conflicts. In the analysis of innovative development conflicts, the composition of the conditions for its emergence has a special place.

This situation can be explained by the fact that the previous specific knowledge and skills become obsolete much faster due to the high pace of technological changes and updates. Subjects should have not only traditional knowledge, but also highly sophisticated equipment and analysis methods, and the skills to use technologies in the implementation of functions that are changing their nature under the influence of traditional approaches in education and new technologies. demand increases.

According to scientists, the "innovative orientation of the task of modern teacher training" requires that it be considered as an integrative education that represents the practical application of the functions of teaching, development and education.

In today's world, the need for innovation is ever-increasing as the development in the field of learning and teaching is growing more dramatically than ever before. This is the reason for increasing interest in introducing innovations in order to increase the efficiency of the process of training specialists in higher education institutions.

Experts emphasize that the following contribute to the emergence of innovative development disputes [7; 31-b]:

- lack of experience and failure to take into account certain consequences when implementing innovations;
- not being able to assess the efficiency of innovation implementation using objective methods before introducing innovations;
- placement of most of the innovations "from above", formality of the approach, poor development of the content of innovations;
- conservatism of thinking and psychological preparation for accepting innovations;
- such as the lack of mutual understanding between the management and employees of the university.

Conflict situations arising from the purpose and action of innovative development are formed as "opposition" to innovations.

The main factors that create the conditions for the escalation of "resistance" in this process can be described through the environment resulting from objective and subjective situations, taking into account this environment, the timely identification of conflict signs allows to resolve it from the initial stage of the conflict dynamics. .

As objective conditions, the following three environments related to the nature of innovative activity can be explained:

1) The need for rapid implementation of innovation: any innovation first appears as an idea, and it is advisable not to delay its implementation, that is, an innovation that is delayed in its implementation loses its status. As a result of the need for rapid implementation of innovation, in most cases, it is observed that innovations are not fully worked out or implemented without careful planning, that is, insufficient resources, requirements for practical skills of subjects are not taken into account, division of work is not taken into account, and this situation can cause signs of conflict.

2) Broadness requirement of innovation: the level of effectiveness is determined depending on the number of subjects and areas covered by any innovation. Innovative activity carried out only in a certain area may not be able to integrate with the entire internal system that has not changed. This nature of innovation causes cases of involvement in innovation processes without

taking into account the needs and abilities of sectors and subjects, which can affect the emergence of signs of conflict.

3) Promotion and promotion of innovation: in the implementation of any innovation, it is important to provide necessary and sufficient promotion to subjects and partners regarding its nature and expected result. As a result of the action carried out due to the need for promotion, in most cases, the initial information about the innovation does not correspond to the practical activity for a certain period of time, which leads to the appearance of signs of conflict between the subjects in the next innovation approach processes. increases the probability of being

The subjective environment of disputes in the innovative development of higher education institutions is directly related to qualifications and desire, and they are grouped as follows:

1) The subject's incompetence in implementing innovations and the need for help in this regard;

2) Predominance of views and values of the subject.

In the implementation of innovations, that is, when innovation is required, the level of readiness of the subject for innovation, the formation of sufficient skills and qualifications in them is important. This involves the consistent implementation of preparation for this activity, taking into account the subject's motivation to participate in innovative activities.

Conflicts in innovative development are influenced by innovative and traditional views and values, that is, the interests, goals and desires of the subjects participating in mutual pedagogical relations, their positions, which lead to the aggravation of the situation as an emotional-stressful effect. takes the main place. For example, professors who have sufficient experience in their field and a certain reputation in the field can always implement an innovative approach, negating the need for new qualifications, encouraging young employees. active in this regard, or, on the contrary, experienced professors and teachers try to keep up with the times, and young people are irresponsible towards innovation.

In our opinion, it is very difficult to eliminate and manage conflict situations that arise in the context of innovative development, and it is difficult for innovators and participating entities to change their positions or conditions when a conflict occurs. Although in some situations there is a decrease in the conflict, it is not guaranteed that this situation is permanent, that the main conflict has not gone into a hidden form, that is, every time one of the two parties has reduced certain resources or lost motivation to solve the conflict, or it arises after an innovative approach. Factors such as the next difficulty or a decrease in attention to the object of the conflict can lead to a renewal of the conflict.

It can be seen from the above that the uncertainty of conflict factors in the conditions of innovative development significantly complicates the process of its resolution. Although the object of the dispute is the only one, i.e. the implemented innovation, the diversity of the environment listed above plays a key role. As a result of the negative impact of this environment, innovations may be completely rejected by the subjects, the process may be derailed and the expected results may not be achieved, material and moral expenses may not pay off, and may lead to various losses. In addition, in the eyes of the subjects, the reduction of confidence in innovation and its result makes it difficult to implement future innovative actions in the institution that are considered very carefully thought out and important.

In innovations without a subject, without direct interventions at a certain stage of the innovation process, the decrease in the level of importance of the introduced innovation - "know-

how", a material and technical difficult situation, a forecast that is not based on a positive result, a waste of time is the source of the dispute. is the main factor. Such a situation not only affects the subjects, but also creates conflicts in the perspective of quick decisions made as a result of protest. In order to determine the causes of an emerging conflict (for example, a pedagogical conflict), to know the periodicity of its occurrence, it is necessary to know the factors that influenced the emergence of the conflict, first of all, which laws (can be natural or artificial) are followed.

First of all, in order not to fall into the above situation in pedagogical processes, to prevent the occurrence of conflicts

- correct and collegial approach to instruction development processes;
- attach special importance to the competence of the instruction developers in creating a document;

- based on the importance of the innovation and the scope of the work, the section included in the instruction, the logical interdependence and sequence of the clauses, the clear indication of the final result and the correct presentation of its legal basis, the implementation of the process It should be strictly taken into account by the head of the organization that approves the instruction that the tasks are clearly indicated.

Not only the importance and effectiveness of the innovation introduced to the higher education institution, but also the ability of the "pedagogue-instructors" who can give the right direction for its development and the ability to clearly and correctly explain the process and control and directly participate in it The high level of responsibility in operating as a company is determined by the prevention of conflicts that may arise at the stages of innovative development. Otherwise, in the processes of innovative development, it leads to conflict between the customers, objects and subjects of this project.

Today, as a result of the use of multimedia tools in the educational process in higher education institutions, many innovations, new methods of teaching, the practical application of tools, at the same time, teachers and students' knowledge of science, development of educational relations, the most important part of society as the main representatives, based on international trends, applying modern educational technologies based on a modern approach and creating sufficient conditions in this regard, in particular, the relevance of issues of training industry representatives is in the first place. Therefore, there is a great need for professors and teachers who are constantly improving their knowledge and skills in order to train the creators of the new, third Renaissance of new Uzbekistan, who are considered to be the successors of the future, into high-potential personnel with the help of interactive methods of learning. This very need is the cause of conflict between subjects. In the era and space of the information age, many professors and teachers in higher education do not have enough skills to know information and communication technologies, create multimedia and use ready-made products. This situation also causes unique conflicts in the innovative development of the higher education institution.

This imposes the task of planning and forecasting in order to achieve the effective result of each stage, starting from the design period of innovations until the end.

This developed organizational model of conflict prevention is intended to create a set of reliable actions for the results of innovative development of higher education institutions.

In the period of innovative development, not to set the demand sharply is one of the elements of preventing the occurrence of conflicts between subjects. In our opinion, the head of the educational institution and the manager of the innovation processes should develop the interest

of the innovators, professors, teachers, students and parents in the innovations at each stage of the innovation processes, its advantages and convenience with the help of easy and optimal methods and tools. It is important to control. In this case, it is necessary to properly plan the organizational and pedagogical processes of adopting innovations.

The dispute that arises in the process of innovative development of higher education institutions is a special type of dispute, and its object is innovation. This conflict between the participants of the innovation process is based on conflicting values, views, mutual special ideas about the content, form and goals of innovative development, experience, "stiffness" where necessary, not striving for innovations and appear under the influence of a relatively negative attitude, and as a result, they oppose each other in the process of developing and implementing innovations in educational, scientific and educational relations. This is due to conflicting values of the participants (innovative and traditional); It is characterized by the opposing actions of the conflicting parties, that is, the action of one party to introduce something new and the opposition of the other party to them [5,117-b].

The results of innovative development are considered to be the final set of completed works, as well as the conclusion of expressing constructive attitudes towards the activities of the participants of the process. When announcing the results, it is necessary not to put too much pressure, be realistic about the situation, and at the same time be careful. It has its own closed, warning, forward-looking methods aimed at continuing the activity of subjects, and determines

practical results when making decisions aimed at preventing conflicts. Any result will consist of rejection, difficult acceptance, "disagreement" and acceptance by the participants of the innovative development process in relation to the prepared conclusions and data. In this case, the management of the higher education institution, innovators should be prepared in advance for situations in which the relationship between the results and the factors that cause conflicts may arise.

As mentioned above, constructive evaluation is directly encouraging, supporting, motivating, striving for creativity, innovation, research, adopting innovations, in a word, giving objective evaluation through tangible and intangible incentives. is done.

According to Sui Szi-Li, social partners, organization leaders, and conflict experts are directly involved in conflict prevention in four main directions - creating objective conditions for preventing the emergence of conflict and its constructive development, establishing the organization's activities. and optimization of organizational and management conditions, elimination of socio-psychological causes of conflict, blocking of personal causes of conflict [6; page 19].

In our opinion, the state and prospects of innovative activity in higher education largely depend on the innovative competence of personnel and their willingness to participate in the innovative process. Conflicts of innovative development arise due to different models of innovative behavior, types of innovative preparation, various conflicts that occur in innovative processes.

Thus, as important indicators describing the process of innovation as an integration process in higher education:

- 1) attitude of subjects of higher education institutions to innovations and innovative values;
- 2) innovation planning, analysis and control;
- 3) level of innovative activity of subjects;
- 4) readiness to develop and accept innovations;
- 5) we will show the cooperative activities of the management of the higher educational institution, innovators and subjects.

In our opinion, in addition to constantly expanding the professional skills and qualifications of professors and specialists, socio-psychological trainings aimed at preventing conflicts, communication and discussion trainings, organizing roundtable discussions with psychologists and conflict experts, students it is effective in preparing for prevention aimed at creating innovations and preventing various conflicts and conflicts that arise during the period of innovative development.

In order to achieve collective support for innovations, first of all, the pedagogue determines the need to form positive attitudes of employees and students towards innovations, to have an emotional impact on them and to direct motivations towards effective results. This is, first of all, the integration of the entities that are the participants of the innovations within the framework of the general development goals of the higher education institution, the development of the conflict management skills of the institution's management, the methods of conducting negotiations in the work process, and the innovation of professors and students during the implementation of innovations. allows to find a solution to a number of tasks, such as taking into account the interests of people and providing direct support to authorized groups for innovation management [6, 236-b].

In this way, at the first stage of the management of innovative development processes, it is possible to achieve an effective result of managing a comprehensive solution to prevent small conflicts that cause complex pedagogical, social and socio-psychological conflicts.

So, the problems of innovative development arise for many reasons. The nature of the reasons can also be different, and the organizational culture, internal climate in the organization, and management style can affect the innovative development of the higher education institution. The ability of the head of a higher education institution or the initiator of innovation to see the possible causes of the obstacles that arise and to work competently with them, in addition, to prevent a number of problems in conflict prevention and to accelerate the process of innovation implementation, the pedagogical team, the innovator's innovative helps to combine ideas and goals. This shows the need to prepare students for conflict prevention and develop master classes and short-term courses for professors and teachers.

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